

SPACE EXPLORATION-A QUEST FOR THE MANKIND.

Abstract: From the time we were created, humans have been piqued their interest. Man has always been exploring the outer space for new avenues both solar and extrasolar system planets. There are few factors that need to be analysed and studied. This paper discusses the various factors considered for space exploration.

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1. Introduction:

Space Exploration generally refers to the use of astronomy and space engineering and technology to explore the outer space [1]. This activity is carried out by humans through manned-space missions and robotic space probes. The history of space exploration started as early as 1608 when telescope was invented. In the year 1968, the first space telescope was launched. In the year 1944, the V-2 rocket [2] was the first to cross the Karman Line. 1949, the BUMPER-WAC became the first human-made object to enter space [3]. The first successful orbital launch was of Soviet's Sputnik-1 in the year 1957. The sputnik-1 was the earth's first artificial satellite [4]. All the above achievements didn't involve any human interaction. From the year 1961, the spacecraft Vostok-1 carried

the first human into the space [5]
.Through these events humanity has proved themselves that it is possible to come out of earth and explore what is known as infinite universe. The universe as we see today is only a drop in the mighty ocean of the cosmic universe. The universe is always ever expanding and many galaxy clusters and star-systems are being formed. They are about a billion galaxies in the universe which have some habitable hotspots. To explore all these places, the power lies in us to use the technology.

2. Space exploration objectives
The main objectives of space exploration:

- To find new planets that can be sustainable for human life.
- To explore and research for any evidence of extra-terrestrial life.

All these objectives were formulated based on the previous missions carried out by different countries. All those missions had these attributes in common.

If as humans we need to understand the basic reasons as why we need to carry out space exploration missions. Many space exploration missions have already captured the imagination of so many people and has found it's way into the movies, comics, arts and many more. To explore the universe we must start our exploration from our own Solar system.

Precisely to classify our solar system, we can have three divisions:

- Hot Zone
- Cold One
- Goldilocks Zone

Our Planet Earth falls in the region of Goldilocks zone. In this zone the planets are comparatively habitable in comparison to other planets such as Mercury, Venus, Uranus and others. For a planet to be in Goldilocks zone, certain conditions must be fulfilled compulsorily. Only then a planet is deemed to be habitable and sustainable for human life.

So, with these things in mind, we proceed to understand how to accomplish our space exploration objectives.

Our first Objective is to find new planets that could sustain human life.

For this objective we need to understand why we need to search for a new planet.

Human interest in the heavens has been universal and enduring. They have been driven to explore the unknown, discover new worlds.

In the quest for a better planet, scientists and researchers have selected our distant neighbour, the Mars. Mars has always been a source of inspiration for scientists and explorers. Robotic Missions have discovered the evidence of water, but life exists beyond earth and that still remains a mystery [6]. But just proving the evidence of water is not justifiable to say that the planet is capable of sustaining human life.

In that case, they are few planets in universe ,that are capable of sustaining the human life.

For the planet to be sustainable, it must lie in the circumstellar habitable zone or CHZ or Goldilocks zone. In this zone, the atmospheric pressure can maintain liquid water on it's surface. A potentially habitable planet implies a terrestrial planet within the circumstellar habitable zone and conditions roughly comparable to those of earth [7]. That sums up our earth-like terminology. Coming to our search for extraterrestrial life, our humans have been fascinated by their portrayal in all sorts of media and art. They even have been hypothesized to exist in the solar system [8]. The search for bio-signatures within the solar system is by studying planetary surfaces and examining meterorites [8]. Whatever the case might be about the

presence of various life forms in the solar systems, much of them are either microorganisms or insect-like creatures. However no article or any theory supports the presence of humanoid-life or advanced civilisations in the cosmological universe.

3. Space Exploration Technologies and Missions

The Technologies used for exploring the space are known as Space Exploration Technologies. As we discussed the objectives previously on why we intend to do so, we shall move on to analysing on the technologies that help us in exploring the space.

The main thing that drives us is the fact that there is something out there that needs to be explored.

Humanity has already been on the pursuit of finding new planets and are on the verge of making them habitable and more human-centric.

The main technologies that we will be looking are:

- Human Spaceflight (Manned Spaceflight) [12]

- Un-Crewed Flight [13]

- Robotic Spaceflight [14]

- Interstellar travel [17]

From time-to-time we as humans wanted to explore and colonise the outer solar system for our own benefit. And as discussed earlier, any planet that we wish to colonise must be able to sustain the human life for a considerable period of time. We shall discuss the about the aforementioned technologies in detail.

Human spaceflight:

Human spaceflight is sometimes referred to as Manned spaceflight or crewed spaceflight is nothing but a spaceflight with crew and passengers on board. It may be operated remotely from the ground or can be operated by the crew on board.

The crew mostly includes: A pilot to pilot the spacecraft, technical crew members and engineers, Physicists, Medical Professionals.

Each crew has their own and important role to play. Though seems exciting, there are numerous hazards that pose an imminent threat to the safety of the brave explorers. We also need to assess the value and the potential of the hazards and the threats that pose to the humans.

Simply relying on the benefits of space exploration does not guarantee us the fact that the missions that are being

organised, planned, executed by the space agencies on the planet do give an output of 90% or more. With each step as the space crew goes towards its destination in the space the dangers come equally close enough to them. Also we need to understand the space environment in order to acclimatize any crew member in the outer space.

Human Spaceflight also involves the act of Extravehicular Activity [20]. Any activity done by an astronaut or a cosmonaut outside a spacecraft most preferably beyond the Earth's Atmosphere.

The First spacewalk was made by the Soviet cosmonaut Alexei Leonov

The activity involves getting out of the spacecraft and then performing experiments, spacewalks, performing repairs on the spacecraft and responding in case of an emergency.

All these events happen in case of Human spaceflight.

Un-crewed Spaceflight: [13]

It's a spaceflight without people on board. Mostly they are either pre-programmed or are controlled by the people on ground.

The Un-crewed spacecraft may have varying levels of autonomy from human input.

The most common examples are the Parker Solar Probe. It is a robotic [14] spacecraft that was launched in the year 2018 to make observations on outer corona and the outer layer of the sun.

These space probes are completely controlled, managed and taken care of by the ground crew.

Mainly probes are sent into the space to those regions that are beyond human

reach, like the sun, Pluto or any exoplanet systems or even the famous intergalactic and interstellar travel probes: The Voyager Probes.

Some other examples include the OREX(Orbital Re-Entry Experiment) by Japan; ARD(Atmospheric Re-Entry Demonstrator) by European Space Agency. These space probes are not meant for any sort of space or astrophysical research. They are used to demonstrate the power behind the experiments.

The final ones that are also included in this category are the Cargo spacecraft [21]. These spacecraft are designed to carry cargo possibly to support space station operations by transporting food, propellant and other supplies.

Now let's talk about the pros and cons of using robotic [14] or un-crewed spaceflight.

The main advantage is that we can use un-crewed spaceflight in order to conduct research on un-accessible areas in our solar system such as the sun or very far regions or cold/icy regions where human intervention is either un-necessary or highly dangerous. Moreover they are remotely operated and hence the chances of space hazards targeted at the humans is completely reduced. When we deploy any robotic [14] spacecraft into the space, at times we might encounter a loss of information due to various reasons like electromagnetic interference by the cosmic rays or any sort of cosmological interference. This can cloud the data that's been coming from the spacecraft due to these interventions. Hence it is

absolutely necessary for the probe to maintain perfect connection of suitable bandwidth and latency in order to communicate smoothly.

The major disadvantage is simply that once the required purpose of the probe is fulfilled then it's discarded and it keeps floating away aimlessly into the space.

Also we can't forget how messy it would be if those space probes keep on adding to the space junk/space debris and causing a major concern to the harmony of the planet.

Interstellar Travel [17]:

The Interstellar travel is the hypothetical way of travelling across space systems or galaxies by using either manned or unmanned spacecraft.

This kind of travel is much more difficult than interplanetary travel, wherein you

would just go to another planet like mars or our moon. Here the distances between the planets are less than 30 astronomical units. On considering time as our resource, we can say that it would take years or even more to travel across such distances.

The various planets, moons, exoplanets and their distances are given in AU

Object	A.U	Light time
Moon	0.0026	1.3 seconds
Sun	1	8 minutes
Venus	0.28	2.41 minutes
Neptune	29.8	4.1 hours
Voyager1	148.7	20.41 hours
Promixa Centauri	262,328	4.24 yrs

With the above table we can realise that travelling to the nearest star i.e Proxima Centauri is also not a considerable option.

The main challenges that we pose are Energy required, time taken, economic feasibility, human sustenance and many more.

There have been numerous proposals for conducting experiments on interstellar travel. Some of the most popular ones are:

- ➔ Suspended Animation
- ➔ Frozen Embryos
- ➔ Island Hopping

Suspended Animation:

This activity involves the temporary cessation of most vital function without death, similar to dormancy and hibernation.

This can be achieved through human hibernation and cryonic preservation.

But sadly enough neither of them are practically possible to take place due to many well-known reasons like economic factors, technological viability etc.. and so on and so forth.

Frozen Embryos:

This might seem a little bit straight out of a Hollywood science fiction movie, but so it seems that it might be possible for us to accomplish that feat. But doing there might be so many complications pertaining to genetic diversity and mutation which might prove a major challenge to space colonisation.

Instead of the new born human beings having a human as their parent, they will be parented by a robot. This might have several psychological effects on the new born beings.

Island Hopping:

The Entire outer space is not empty or devoid of resources. Rather it is filled with numerous substances and materials which can be used wisely throughout the journey and this feat can be achieved using the technique of Island Hopping. By hopping through the solar system scouring for the natural resources and utilising them throughout the journey.

Conclusions:

1. The main purpose of space exploration is to carry out research as well as to colonise the space as a standby in order to prepare for the Big Move
2. The main usage of Un-Manned Spaceflight might be tuned up little

more such as using it for studying the effects of substances in the outer space.

3. The Technologies like Suspended Animation may not be a viable idea for the humans to travel a long distance into the outer space. So far no one has ventured beyond the CHZ as humans. The only things that went as far were the Voyager Space Probes.
4. Implementing Space Colonisation using Frozen Embryos has a very deep psychological effect on the human brain whose effects are far beyond the comprehension of any average human. Their cognitive skills are different from what we have.
5. Island Hopping seems to be viable enough, but considering time as a resource it is not economically possible.

References:

1. Space Exploration Wikipedia

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Space_exploration#:~:text=Space%20exploration%20is%20the%20use,space%20probes%20and%20human%20space%20flight.

2. V-2 rocket wikipedia

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/V-2_rocket

3. NASA Website

https://www.nasa.gov/mission_pages/explorer/bumper.html

4. sputnik-1

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Sputnik_1

5. Vostok-1

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Vostok_1

6. Why we explore.. NASA

https://www.nasa.gov/exploration/whyweexplore/why_we_explore_main.html#.X1keJWgzaM8

7. List of potentially habitable planets

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/List_of_potentially_habitable_exoplanets#:~:text=A%202015%20review%20concluded%20that%20light%20years%20away%20C%20respectively.&text=The%20potentially%20habitable%20planet%20TOI,only%20100%20light%20years%20away.

8. Asteroid Mining

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Asteroid_mining

9. Space-based solar power

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Space-based_solar_power

10. Non-Rocket spacelaunch

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Non-rocket_spacelaunch

11. Space Manufacturing

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Space_manufacturing

12. Human spaceflight

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Human_spaceflight

13. uncrewed spaceflight

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Uncrewed_spacecraft

14. Robotic spaceflight

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Robotic_spacecraft

15. Colonisation of the Moon

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Colonization_of_the_Moon

16. Colonisation of the outer Solar system

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Colonization_of_the_outer_Solar_System

17. Interstellar Travel

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Interstellar_travel

18. Intergalactic travel

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Intergalactic_travel

19.https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Suspended_animation

Suspended animation